

Implementation of Economic Policies Facing Covid 19 in Supporting Nonmilitary Defense

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ABSTRACT: Non-military defense is structured into a security function for public safety which includes natural disaster management, humanitarian operations, socio-culture, economics, defense psychology, which is basically related to awareness of state defense and technology development. The government's economic policies in facing Covid 19 have an impact on Non-military Defense, especially in the economic sector, including causing prolonged uncertainty so that investment weakens and has implications for the cessation of business in all fields that threaten the nation's disintegration. The research objective is to provide government input on the implementation and strategy of economic policies in dealing with Covid 19. Research using qualitative methods is aimed at understanding social phenomena from the perspective of participants. The results achieved are in accordance with the Policy Implementation theory that the government needs a strategy to prepare a strategy through a professional grand design or map, increased coordination between central and local governments and appropriate economic policy setting, especially budget.

KEYWORDS: Economic Policy, Covid 19, State Defense, and Non-Military Defense

INTRODUCTION

National defense in facing non-military threats places Ministries and institutions outside the field of defense as the Main Elements in Presidential Regulation No. 8 of 2021 concerning general national defense policy. Based on the development of the strategic environment, it is predicted that there will be threats that need to be considered in defense policy making. The types of threats consist of military threats, non-military threats and hybrid threats. These threats are both current and potential. Potential threats include open conflicts, nuclear weapons, economic crises, pandemics and foreign immigrants.

Non-military defense is a state defense force that is built within the framework of national development to achieve national welfare and is prepared to face non-military threats. The non-military defense layer is structured into the security function for public safety which includes the handling of natural disasters and other humanitarian operations, socio-culture, economics, defense psychology, which is basically related to the thinking of state defense awareness, and technology development (Kementerian Pertahanan, 2016).

The research objective is to provide government input on the implementation and strategy of economic policies in dealing with Covid 19. Research using qualitative methods is aimed at understanding social phenomena from the perspective of participants. In accordance with the theory of Policy Implementation, the government needs a strategy to prepare a strategy through a grand design or professional map, increased coordination between the central and local governments and the setting of appropriate economic policies, especially the budget.

At the end of 2019, to be precise in December, the world was shocked by an incident that was suspected of being a pneumonia case whose etiology was unknown whose case came from the city of Wuhan, China. China identified pneumonia on January 7, 2020 as a new type of coronavirus. The statement "urgent notice on the treatment of pneumonia of unknown cause" has been issued by the Wuhan Municipal Health Committee (Hanoatubun, 2020).

The consequences of the Covid-19 pandemic will have an impact on the global economy. China is the country with the second largest economy in the world. There was an economic slowdown in China as a result of the impact of Covid-19, last year economic growth in China was 6.1% to around 3.8% this year. Population mobilization in a highly connected world has caused the current pandemic to continue to spread rapidly until the entire world is affected by this pandemic. The world economy is predicted to reach -1.1% in 2020 by JP Morgan. Then, the world economy is predicted to reach - 2.2% by the EIU, -1.9% predicted by Fitch EIU predicts minus 2.2%, Fitch, and -3% predicted by the IMF. These economic predictions are very worrying for people in the world (Iskandar, Possumah, & Aqbar, 2020).

Currently the world economy is experiencing heavy pressure caused by the covid-19 virus or what is known as the corona virus. This virus is coming to be known by the wider community in 2020. Seeing economic development and economic influence

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not only in the economic sphere, but health and culture also has an impact on the economy. Evidenced by the spread of the corona virus has a negative impact on the economy. Corona virus greatly affects the economy in 3 main sectors, namely the capital market sector, debt securities trading and gold trading (Rahmadia, 2020). The World Bank defines economic hardship as a low level of welfare. A common measure related to economic difficulties around the world is the inability to meet basic needs, which is reflected, among others, through household consumption. The pressure on consumption due to the pandemic has been seen in the first quarter, household consumption was 2.84%. This figure decreased drastically compared to consumption in the first quarter of 2020 (year on year / yoy) of 5.02% and compared to consumption in the fourth quarter of 2020 of 4.97% (Fah20). It is important to map the impact of COVID-19 on global political economy in order to formulate future policies in fighting the pandemic. That the political economy sector is most vulnerable to the impact of COVID-19 so that it can lead to a trade war (Kusno, 2020)

The Covid 19 pandemic has prompted the Indonesian government to issue regulations / policies related to its handling. The policies in question include Presidential Decree No. 9 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Presidential Decree No. 7 of 2020 concerning the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19, Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 21 of 2020 concerning Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in the context of the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 and Presidential Decree No. 12 of 2020 concerning the Designation of Non-Natural Disasters of the spread of Covid-19 as a National Disaster. The regulations that have been made are alternative solutions to problems that can be seen in terms of the health, bureaucracy, politics and finances of the State of Indonesia as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic (Ambar & Mas'uid, 2020).

The government policy is still considered not optimal. Spokesperson for the Task Force for Handling Covid-19 Prof. Wiku Adisasmito revealed the results of the evaluation of the PPKM in Java and Bali which took place from 11-25 January 2021 were not as expected, based on indicators for active cases of Covid-19, as many as 46 districts / cities have increased, 24 regencies / cities have decreased, and three districts / cities have not changed. Based on the indicators of death cases, it was recorded that 44 districts / cities experienced an increase, and 29 districts / cities experienced a decrease. Meanwhile, based on the recovery indicator, 37 districts / cities experienced a decline and 36 districts / cities increased.

The government makes fiscal stimulus as a form of intervention in stabilizing the economy. Apart from aiming at dealing with health and economic recovery, the stimulus is aimed at overcoming extreme economic difficulties through a social safety net for low-income people (MBR). Other forms include electricity subsidies and the expansion of social assistance, including in the form of basic food cards, family hope program (PKH) and pre-employment cards carried out by the government to help people affected by the COVID-19 pandemic (Yuliana, 2020)

LITERATURE REVIEWS

Some of the stages of the policy process, which lie between the formulation and consequences that will arise by a policy, are the definition of a policy (Edward III, 1980). In a policy, there are 4 interconnected aspects in its implementation, namely aspects of communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure (Wahyudi, 2016). This theory is interesting to apply because it discusses 4 aspects that are relevant to government policy, especially the handling of Covid 19 from an economic point of view.

Bureaucracy is defined as the power, influence, or authority possessed by government officials (Albrow, 1996). Today the bureaucracy is often defined as an institution or institution that carries out the functions and responsibilities of the state. In other words, the bureaucracy is the engine room of the state. Bureaucracy is also often defined as an organization of officials who are arranged hierarchically and appointed to carry out certain public goals (Halevy, 1983). This bureaucracy for researchers is a highlight that needs to be raised regarding the handling of Covid 19. The author looks at the bureaucracy related to the lack of synchronization between the central and local governments in handling Covid 19.

The policies made by the government in handling Covid-19 can indirectly lead to a decline in economic growth in Indonesia. The impact on the economic sector due to the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia includes layoffs, the occurrence of PMI Manufacturing Indonesia, decreased imports, increased prices (inflation) as well as losses in the tourism sector which led to a decrease in occupancy. As a result of this, it is hoped that the Indonesian government will be more alert in dealing with the decline in economic growth in Indonesia as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic (Yamali, 2020). This research shows that the bureaucratic structure of the central and local governments is still not well established.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in low investor sentiment towards the market which in turn has led to a negative trend. Strategic fiscal and monetary measures are needed to provide economic stimulus. As the COVID-19 pandemic case develops, the market is more volatile in a negative direction. Not only that, the slowdown in the global economy, especially Indonesia's export activities to China, also had a significant impact on the Indonesian economy. (Nasution., 2020). This is based on a sensitivity analysis which explains that the current slowdown in the global economy has had a major impact on Indonesia's economic growth with low investor sentiment.

Analysis of the impact of covid-19 on the socio-economic conditions of traders in the Klaten and Wonogiri markets. With the Covid-19 virus pandemic, the economy has experienced a decline, especially in market traders who experienced a 50% decline in turnover and income. (Azimah, 2020). Locally, in some regions, there has been a significant decrease in turnover and income, this of course requires government performance from the central level to the regional level in an integrated and directed manner.

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If the large-scale restrictions are prolonged and / or expanded to other cities, the national economic loss due to the Covid-19 pandemic will automatically increase the impact of the loss and can be projected based on a comparison of time and area. For convenience, the discussion of losses is divided into groups of national, sectoral, corporate and individual losses. (Wardoyo, 2020). This research is relevant to the current condition that there are losses in several sectors, both personal and organizational, which are prone to impact the nation's disintegration and endanger defense, especially non-military defense.

If associated with this theory developed by scientists from the United States that the theory of behaviorism includes all behavior, including countermeasures or responses to a stimulus or stimulus. This means that there is always a link between the stimulus and the response to human behavior. Jhon B. Watson (1878 - 1958). If there is an event that is national in nature and has an impact on national vulnerability, a stimulus or stimulation received by a person has been observed, it can also be predicted that the response of that person to act against the law on the grounds of survival (Survival). Responding to this, it can be seen that the communication carried out by the regional government and the central government in the context of handling Covid 19 has not been optimal (B. Watson, 1930).

METHODS

The research method used in this study used a descriptive qualitative approach and literature study. Descriptive research is research conducted to describe and describe the current state of the research object as it is based on facts (Moleong L. J., 2008). Denzin distinguishes four kinds of triangulation as a technique for checking the validity of the data that utilizes sources, methods, investigators, and by theory (Moleong, 1994). Data analysis in this article is carried out through: 1. Data reduction, namely by summarizing, sorting out the main data, then focusing and compiling the data systematically. 2. Display data, which is presenting certain data in the form of matrices, charts, charts, or networks if needed. 3. Data verification.

The model proposed by George C. Edward III, III, is top down and suitable to be implemented at a structured bureaucratic level in a government institution, where each hierarchical level has a role in accordance with its function in the elaboration of policies. which will be implemented and facilitate the implementation of a policy at each level of the bureaucracy starting from the departmental level (central government), to the level of implementers in the field. Edward III's model directs the understanding of policy implementation variables and the relationship between variables by determining the role of each variable. Communication is needed by every policy implementer to know what to do. Resources ensure support for the effectiveness of policy implementation. The bureaucratic structure describes the composition of the duties of the implementers of policies, breaks them down in details of tasks and establishes standard operating procedures (Edward III, 1980).

The disposition according to Edward in (Widodo, 2018) states that disposition is the willingness, desire and tendency of policy actors to carry out policies seriously so that what is the goal of the policy can be realized. If policy implementation is to be successful in an effective and efficient manner, the implementers not only know what to do and have the will to implement the policy, but also must have the will to implement the policy (Edward III, 1980)

RESULT

Some of the stages of the policy process, which lie between the formulation and consequences that will arise by a policy, are the definition of a policy (Edward III, 1980). In a policy, there are 4 interconnected aspects in its implementation, namely aspects of communication, resources, disposition and bureaucratic structure (Wahyudi, 2016).

In terms of communication, it can be seen that the efforts made by the government have not been maximized and it seems that they are not serious about handling the COVID-19 pandemic. This can be seen from indicators including the government not preparing a strategy through a grand design or road map in the context of handling the COVID-19 pandemic.

In terms of resources. Human resources are limited in handling Covid 19. Health workers are limited to being able to serve the community, as well as limited human resources in implementing large-scale restrictions to prevent the transmission of the Covid 19 virus. Budget resources are limited. The government issued a Government Regulation in lieu of Law or Perpu Number 1 of 2020, which later became Law Number 2 of 2020. The Ministry of Finance allocated a budget for handling Covid-19 for MSMEs, corporate financing and business incentives. However, the budgetary power that the government has prepared in order to handle Covid 19 has not been sufficient in terms of numbers. Facilities and infrastructure. In general, infrastructure is limited compared to the total population infected with the Corona virus.

From a Disposition Point of view. It can be seen that all policies in Law 2 of 2020, especially policies in the field of state finances, have basically been implemented and implemented based on the assessment and use of factual data and the impact of the Covid-19 threat. From a statutory standpoint, it has conformed to the principles in accordance with the respective leading sectors.

In terms of non-military defense. If the government is not alert in handling Covid 19, it will have an impact on the disintegration of the nation. National defense in facing non-military threats places Ministries and institutions outside the field of defense as the Main Elements. Here it demands the main role of the Ministries / Institutions involved in supporting non-military defense, especially in the economic field. The types of threats consist of military threats, non-military threats and hybrid threats. These threats are both current and potential. Potential threats include open conflicts, nuclear weapons, economic crises, pandemics

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and foreign immigrants. Non-military defense, also known as non-military defense, is a state defense force built within the framework of national development to achieve national prosperity and is prepared to face non-military threats. The non-military defense layer is composed of security functions for public safety which include the handling of natural disasters and other humanitarian operations, socio-culture, economics, defense psychology, which are basically related to the thinking of state defense awareness, and technology development.

DISCUSSION

Communication has a very important role in the delivery of a policy, this is so that the policies to be conveyed can be understood properly by the implementers. Communication includes all behavior, including countermeasures or responses to a stimulus or stimulus. This means that there is always a link between the stimulus and the response to human behavior (B.Watson, 1930).

Based on document search, it is known that there are at least 4 (four) main problems of government communication in handling Covid-19 in Indonesia, namely: inaccurate data and information, lack of socialization related to several issues, low public trust, and ineffective communication of government organizations. Therefore, the House of Representatives needs to encourage the government to revise government communication guidelines in handling Covid-19 and to optimize the role of the Ministry of Communication and Informatics. (Ardiyanti, 2020)

The policy recommendation document for the civil society coalition compiled jointly by Indonesia Corruption Watch, the Indonesia Budget Center, the Indonesian Forum for Transparency, and Transparency International highlights the communication problem as one of the government's unpreparedness in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic. The various policies issued to deal with the spread of Covid-19 were inconsistent, not transparent, and caused a contraction in communication, especially between competent state institutions and between the central government and local governments.

Media communication is still ineffective because it gives too much confidence and lacks consistency. Therefore, the Indonesian Parliament should encourage the government to increase its effectiveness in conducting media communication during the Covid-19 pandemic. Regarding the main obstacle is the controversy between patient privacy v.s. In the interest of preventing the spread of the pandemic, the House of Representatives should take an inventory of any provisions that are contradicting each other in the Law and carry out an alignment of these various provisions by taking into account the culture of the community in dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic. (Ardiyanti, 2020).

Member of Commission IX from the PKS Faction, NettyPrasetyani at Koran Sindonews, 20/7/2020 assessed that the communication carried out by the government was not optimal, it was not serious in handling the COVID-19 pandemic. The indicator is that the government does not appear to be preparing a grand design or road map to reduce the COVID-19 pandemic.

The head of the Covid 19 acceleration task force and the Head of the National Disaster Management Agency (BNPB) DoniMonardo admitted that the problem of improving the Covid 19 test using the PCR method was in the limited number of human resources.

Organizations and their human resources must navigate through the harsh effects of the novel coronavirus disease (COVID-19). Such external crises require a dynamism of the HR system to address the growing concerns of all sectors around the world and in particular, Indonesia's formal sector and its employees. In an effort to ensure that both parties are well served after the COVID-19 crisis period, there is a need to reintegrate existing human resource practices and procedures. Transcending crises will require learning, innovation and adaptation. HR practices need to be modified, rebuilt and put into practice (Rusilowati, 2020)

Human Resources means integrated expertise that comes from the power of thought and physical power possessed by each person. Those who do and their nature are done still have a close relationship such as descent and their environment, while their work performance is motivated by a desire to fulfill their desires (Hasibuan, 2003)

The Director of Primary Health Services of the Ministry of Health, Saraswati, at the national sindows, revealed that currently puskesmas still lack Human Resources (HR) to carry out tracing in order to enforce 3T, namely tracing, testing, and Covid-19 treatment. For tracing that is mass and representative, it also requires additional power. Leaders in facing the Covid-19 pandemic and the new normal have done 3 things, namely remote working, employee productivity, and upskilling for digital (Bimanti Esthi, 2020)

In terms of budget resources, the Minister of Home Affairs, Tito Karnavian, revealed the problem of handling Covid-19 in the regions. One of them is the limited budget for several regions in Indonesia. the strength of the central government has been sought to deal with Covid-19. However, the government's steps in Jakarta have not run optimally in the regions due to budget problems.

The budget deficit policy, which has always been applied in state expenditure budget management, is a policy that is less responsive to economic conjunctions. In addition, budget policies need to be responsive and flexible in addressing economic conjunctions. With responsive and flexible policies, a surplus, deficit, or balanced budget is implemented in order to overcome and anticipate economic developments / cycles so that if a recession occurs it will not have fatal consequences for the national economy and deteriorate public welfare(Subekan, 2020)

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The problem faced by the government is not only the limited budget allocated for handling Covid-19, but also the very low absorption in various ministries. The low absorption of the development budget in the first and second quarters of the current fiscal year is actually nothing new.

Minister of Finance Sri Mulyani Indrawati told Tempo magazine on February 8, 2021, that out of the Rp 695 trillion budget allocation for handling Covid-19 and the current national economic recovery (PEN), Rp 444 trillion has been realized. "It has been implemented at 63.3 percent of the ceiling.

The local government argues that the budget refocusing policy is based on the provisions in the Presidential Instruction on Activity Refocusing, Budget Reallocation, and Procurement of Goods and Services in the Context of Accelerating Handling of COVID-19. Such an arrangement is of course not too strong, in fact it will have the potential to become a gap in the occurrence of mensrea (evil intentions) for implementers of government policies, especially both budget users / power users. What should be regulated in the budgeting policy related to the budget refocusing policy is through the issuance of a Government Regulation in Lieu of a Law which is the basis for substitution in the Law on Regional Government which has been the basis for the legality of the regional financial policy process as well as other regulations (Junaidi, 2020)

When viewed from the facilities and infrastructure. Spokesperson for the Covid-19 Handling Task Force Wiku Adisasmito appealed to regional health facilities to immediately coordinate with the center if there are obstacles to medical equipment facilities and infrastructure. It is intended that health services run smoothly.

Preparedness does not only concern human resources but also facilities and infrastructure. Preparedness is carried out based on the principle of overcoming the outbreak, namely in the prevention, detection and response phases. Cross-sector cooperation is needed, both with related ministries / agencies and local governments. The Indonesian Parliament, especially Commission IX, has an important role to play in monitoring the readiness of the government in dealing with Covid-19 in accordance with Law no. 6 of 2018 concerning Health Quarantine and Law no. 4 of 1984 concerning Outbreaks of Infectious Diseases (Suri, 2020)

Knowledge ($p = 0.001$), attitude ($p = 0.000$), PHBS ($p = 0.000$), and infrastructure ($p = 0.000$) are related to the implementation of health protocols on micro-entrepreneurs. The transmission of Covid-19 is very fast so it is necessary to provide education to residents regarding the causes of Covid-19 transmission, including not doing Clean and Healthy Living Behaviors (PHBS) or Washing Hands with Soap (CTPS) and environmental factors (Nismawati, 2020)

The COVID-19 pandemic has caused many hospitals in Indonesia to experience difficulties in both management and infrastructure in providing services because the number of patients has increased in a short time. A modeling-based research predicts that next week hospitals in Jakarta and five provinces with the most cases of corona infection will decrease their ability to treat severe patients due to COVID-19 who need intensive care rooms (ICU) and ventilators due to limited facilities.

Some of the infrastructure that can be used to consult health conditions include Halodoc, Gojek, Alodokter and so on. This digital health service makes it easy to consult about health conditions and how to recognize symptoms of the SARS-CoV-2 virus, the cause of the COVID-19 disease without having to go to the hospital.

With the existence of PSBB in accordance with Government Regulation No. 21 of 2020, in the education sector, public services, all places of worship, shopping centers, restaurants and tourism places also experience difficult things in development (Misno, Junediyono, & Nurhadi, 2020). This social or physical distancing has an effect on decreasing overall economic activity (Iskandar, Possumah, & Aqbar, 2020)

Judging from the Bureaucratic Structure, the old structure has been dissolved and the formation of a new structure for handling Covid-19. Negative narrative and the slow response of the government to the spread of COVID-19. The narratives conveyed by the political elite before COVID-19 entered Indonesia show no sense of crisis that threatens to slow down decision making. Weak coordination between stakeholders, especially between the central government and local governments. This asynchrony of coordination has resulted in unstable control of the corona virus. Citizens' disobedience to the government's appeal. The impact is that efforts to deal with it have stalled because it is not supported by the wider community (Agustino, 2020).

The new structure in the form of a committee in addition to dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic also handles the economy chaired by Minister of state-owned enterprises Erick Thohir. With this new structure it is hoped that the handling of Covid-19 can be successful. Several factions in the House of Representatives appreciated the President's steps to change the bureaucratic structure of handling Covid-19 in Indonesia. With this new structure, there are two emphases to be achieved, namely the health aspect and the economic aspect.

The Covid 19 pandemic has prompted the Indonesian government to issue regulations / policies related to its handling. The regulations / policies in question include Presidential Decree No. 9 of 2020 concerning Amendments to Presidential Decree No. 7 of 2020 concerning the Task Force for the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19, Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia No. 21 of 2020 concerning Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) in the context of the Acceleration of Handling Covid-19 and Presidential Decree No. 12 of 2020 concerning the Designation of Non-Natural Disasters of the spread of Covid-19 as a National Disaster. The regulations that have been made are alternative solutions to problems that can be seen in terms of the health, bureaucracy, politics and finances of the Indonesian State resulting from the Covid-19 pandemic (Ambar & Mas'uid, 2020).

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The nine regulations that have been issued by the government are the basis for the allocation, distribution and stabilization policies that can be carried out. The first step is that the government is obliged to allocate qualified inputs and resources to its policy orientation (Allocation Policy), namely to new vulnerable groups affected by Covid-19, including business groups who need crowds, groups of casual daily workers, street vendors, workers affected by layoffs, farmers, the poor, and so on (Eddyono & Suzanna, 2020)

The externalities of Covid-19 have weakened their opportunities to generate daily income, resulting in massive layoffs of workers who reached 1,943,916 people consisting of 114,340 companies. This incident will experience an increase in numbers that will continue to increase if this pandemic lasts a long time. In addition, with the appeal to "stay at home" to the community, it will significantly reduce people's income from their routines, very limited economic activity, and other influences that follow (Mas'udi & Winanti, 2020).

The budget allocation must take into account various dimensions. Don't let the budget for financial stimulus exceed the cost of treating Covid-19. Moreover, positive cases of Covid-19 are still rising. This should still be a major concern. This means that the proportion of work programs is divided equally. Should not prioritize economic recovery and leave health care. Both must be done simultaneously.

From the Disposition point of view that every policy implementation instructed by superiors through communicative, persuasive orders and the behavior of a swift administrator, the policy or program implementation will run well.

Emotional response to sadness 45.5%, fear 39.4%, online news media as a source of information 45.5%, social media 36.4%, to get information, respondents prefer health practitioners 45.5%, health authorities 33.3%, respondents expect free examinations and treatment 42.4 %, health education 3.6%, preventive action taken by respondents, namely washing hands 81.8%, using masks 12.1%. It can be seen that the empathy of the Indonesian people is still relatively high, for online news media it is used as a media source in getting news, and health practitioners gain the public's trust as informants regarding Covid-19, while the public hopes that there will be free examinations and treatment for people who have signs and symptoms of the corona virus , and preventive action taken by the community is to wash hands(Sudiro, 2020)

All policies in Law 2 of 2020, especially policies in the field of state finances that have been implemented at this time, have been based on an assessment and use factual data and the impact of the Covid-19 threat. Law 2/2020 was issued to provide protection for the lives of people who are highly threatened by the Covid-19 pandemic, both from their health, safety, social and economic aspects.

Thus, through this law, the government seeks to carry out rapid assessments and calculations to save people from the impact of the pandemic. Therefore, a number of assistance has been disbursed, ranging from assistance with health costs, support for social and economic assistance, to assistance for small and medium enterprises.

With the issuance of Law 2/2020, the government claims that there have been a number of improvements to the country's economic conditions in the second quarter. Some of these improvements, for example, international trade, which has boosted tax performance and public consumption, which experienced a rebound, although still weak. Then, the economy in the construction sector is considered to have begun to increase, domestic production has begun to grow, even indicators in the manufacturing sector have also increased, so that export-import activity shows an improving trend.

The government must be alert in making strategic policies, if the government is not alert it will have an impact on the vulnerability of social disasters, and it will be very easy for other unwanted conflicts to occur (Barro, Ursúa, & Weng, 2020). However, it cannot be denied that the policies and regulations that have been set by the government will have various impacts, one of which we will discuss in this paper is the economic impact. In addition to the economy being the most important factor in human life, this economic factor is also a supporting factor for national development because the economic growth of a good country can increase a national development (Hanoatubun, 2020).

There needs to be a strategy that must be carried out by the government, among others in carrying out its functions, there are several things that are the focus of the Government.

First, the Government in managing the budget, especially the budget for handling COVID-19, is required to be carried out prudently (prudent) and is required to carry out strict supervision involving all elements. From an economic perspective, the Government appears to have targeted recipients of the social safety net budget, which focuses on the implementation mechanism in the field. The budget must be received by those entitled to receive it in a timely manner and in the right amount, this of course must be a major concern for the government.

Second, in order to face economic hardship in society, the Government needs to implement a program to increase investment on data accompanied by analysis to provide relevant information for decision making.

Third, the Government, in order to maintain and stabilize mental health conditions due to economic difficulties during the ongoing pandemic, is carried out by utilizing mass media that can educate the public to mitigate the transmission of the corona virus.

Fourth, from an economic point of view, the government must focus on preventive policies (substantive) and focus more on economic regulatory policies. There is a need for a strategy to increase coordination between the central and regional governments so that it can be well-established, so that it is hoped that economic policies to face Covid 19 can be implemented as expected.

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CONCLUSION

In terms of communication, the government has not prepared a strategy through a grand design or road map in the context of handling the COVID-19 pandemic. It can be seen that the efforts made by the government have not been maximized and it seems that they are not serious about handling the COVID-19 pandemic.

In terms of resources. Limited budget resources. The government issued a Government Regulation in lieu of Law or Perpu Number 1 of 2020, which later became Law Number 2 of 2020. The Ministry of Finance allocated a budget for handling Covid-19 for MSMEs, corporate financing and business incentives. However, the budgetary power that the government has prepared in the context of handling Covid 19 has not been sufficient in terms of numbers. Human resources are limited in handling Covid 19. Health workers are limited to being able to serve the community, as well as limited human resources in implementing large-scale limiting rules to prevent transmission of the Covid 19 virus. . Facilities and infrastructure. In general, infrastructure is limited compared to the total population infected with the Corona virus.

From a Disposition Point of view. From a statutory standpoint, it has conformed to the principles in accordance with the respective leading sectors. It can be seen that all policies in Law 2 of 2020, especially policies in the field of state finances, have basically been implemented and implemented based on the assessment and use of factual data and the impact of the Covid-19 threat.

Nonmilitary Defense. The types of threats consist of military threats, non-military threats and hybrid threats. These threats are both current and potential. Potential threats include open conflicts, nuclear weapons, economic crises, pandemics and foreign immigrants. The non-military defense layer is composed of security functions for public safety which include the handling of natural disasters and other humanitarian operations, socio-culture, economics, defense psychology, which are basically related to the thinking of state defense awareness, and technology development. National defense in facing non-military threats places Ministries and institutions outside the field of defense as the Main Elements. Here it demands the main role of the Ministries / Institutions involved in supporting non-military defense, especially in the economic field.

LIMITATION

In terms of communication based on document search, it is known that there are at least 4 (four) main problems of government communication in handling Covid-19 in Indonesia, namely: inaccurate data and information, lack of socialization regarding several issues, low public trust, and ineffective communication of government organizations (Ardiyanti, 2020). In this study, there are limitations in the absence of a discussion of how the government should do it. In this case, encouraging the government to revise government communication guidelines in handling Covid-19 and encourage optimization of the role of the Ministry of Communication and Information Technology.

In a study on the weak coordination among stakeholders, especially between the central government and local governments. This asynchrony of coordination has resulted in unstable control of the corona virus. Citizens' disobedience to the government's appeal. The impact is that efforts to deal with it have stalled because it is not supported by the wider community. (Agustino, 2020). This opinion requires an appropriate solution on the bureaucratic side by requiring the government to allocate qualified inputs and resources to its policy orientation (Allocation Policy), namely to new vulnerable groups affected by Covid-19.

The local government argues that the budget refocusing policy is based on the provisions in the Presidential Instruction on Activity Refocusing, Budget Reallocation, and Procurement of Goods and Services in the Context of Accelerating Handling of COVID-19 (Junaidi, 2020). If we analyze the arrangement, of course it will not be strong, it will actually result in an unfavorable gap for implementers of government policies, especially both budget users / power users.

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